

STUDY OF VIBRATION MODAL ESTIMATION FOR COMPOSITE BEAM WITH PZT THIN FILM SENSOR SYSTEM

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SUMMARY: In the present paper, a lead zirconate titanates (PZT) thin film is adopted as a vibration sensor. The PZT thin film sensor is made by the hydrothermal method. A set of these films is sandwiched between flexible electric circuit sheets to build the smart layer. Two types of point sensors systems (PSS) are selected as the sensor system for vibration modal estimation of composite beams. One is an array of point sensors system (APSS) and another is a distributed point sensors system (DPSS). The experiment is conducted by sinusoidal forced vibration tests. The capabilities of PSSs for modal estimation of the composite beam are experimentally demonstrated.

KEYWORDS: PZT thin film sensor, point sensors system (PSS), Array of point sensors system (APSS), distributed point sensors system (DPSS), modal estimation, smart composites, hydrothermal method.

INTRODUCTION

Recently, much attention has been paid to studies of smart materials and structures. The smart materials and structures have sensors and actuators in order to adapt external stimuli. The smart materials and structures will be adopted as space structures, airplanes and huge constructions to improve their reliabilities. Host materials of the smart materials and structure are ceramics, metals, composite materials and so on. In those host materials, the composites is most suitable for constructing the smart materials and structures in its manufacturing process. The smart materials and structures which are adopted the composite materials as host material are called smart composites.

On the other hands, a new device called a smart layer has been proposed[1]. The smart layer consists of dielectric films, sensors, actuators and embedded electric circuits. The smart layer not only looks like the composites lamina, but also it can be handed like the composite lamina. Thus, the smart layer is more ease to construct the smart materials and structures than conventional devices. Mostly smart layers use piezoelectric materials as sensors and actuators.

The piezoelectric material is one of the most attractive devices to construct the smart

materials and structures. The principal commercially available industrial piezoelectric materials are the piezoceramics, such as the PZT. They are available in broad range of properties to suit diverse applications.

In addition, PZT thin films have been developed by a variety of methods such as RF sputtering, metal-organic decomposition and sol-gel processing. Since these methods generally require a high temperature treatment above 500°C to crystallize the films during or after the processing, it often results in cracking or peeling of the films, because of the shrinkage due to the crystallization of deposited amorphous films. On the other hands, the hydrothermal method which was proposed by UBE Industries, Ltd. is a new attractive fabrication process for preparing the PZT thin films. Advantages of the hydrothermal method are relatively low preparing temperature and film uniformity over large areas. Besides, the PZT thin films fabricated by the hydrothermal method are thin and flexible. Thus, this device is more suitable for constructing the smart layer.

In this paper, the smart layer which uses the PZT thin film sensor system is constructed. Two types of PSSs are chosen. One is the array of point sensors system and another is the distributed point sensors system. The smart layer is attached on the surface of a composite beam. The vibration modal estimation for the composite beam with a smart layer is experimentally demonstrated.

PZT THIN FILM[2],[3]

The fabrication process of PZT thin films by hydrothermal method is summarized as shown in Fig.1. Aqueous solution of lead nitrate, zirconium chloride oxide octahydrate, titanium tetrachloride and potassium hydroxide were used as starting materials. Some pieces of titanium foil were placed in Teflon beaker containing the 700ml aqueous solution in an autoclave as schematically shown in Fig.2. As the first process, some pieces of titanium foil as substrates were reacted with the mixed solution containing lead nitrate, zirconium chloride oxide octahydrate, titanium tetrachloride and potassium hydroxide to nucleate crystals on the substrate. They were poured into the autoclave and then heated to 150-200°C for 0-12hr. As the second process, the PZT thin films prepared by the first process on some pieces of titanium foil were also used as substrates. These substrates were also reacted with mixed solution containing lead nitrate, zirconium chloride oxide octahydrate, titanium tetrachloride and potassium hydroxide as 100-150°C for 0-12hr. Film thickness was increased by repeating the second process.

Fig.1: Flow diagram for the fabrication process of PZT thin film sensor.

Fig.2: Schematic illustration of PZT thin film fabrication equipment using an autoclave.

Fig.3: Configuration of PZT thin film s.

The cross-section of the PZT thin film is schematically shown in Fig.3. The PZT thin film of which the film thickness of PZT is $6.5\mu\text{m}$ and that of Ti substrate is $50\mu\text{m}$ is adopted as test specimens. Au electrodes with electrical stability are sputtered on the surfaces of PZT thin films. The thickness is $1500\text{-}2000\text{\AA}$. The hydrothermal method permits one to easily fabricate large sided PZT thin films having not only a flat surface, but also curved one. In fact, they can be cut with a scissors so as to obtain the arbitrary geometry. That is, they are flexible and have a possibility to give a designer more freedom for constructing actual structures.

POINT SENSORS SYSTEM (PSS)

A point sensor is defined as one whose size is smaller than the wavelength of structural motion.[4] There are two types of point sensors systems.

Distributed Point Sensors System (DPSS)

The DPSS is shown in Fig.4. It has several point sensors, but the signals from the sensors are not combined. The DPSS can be used to estimate an absolute amplitude and phase at each point. However, this system requires a multi-channel data processing system.

Fig.4: Configuration of distributed point sensors system.

Array of Point Sensors System (APSS)[4]

The APSS is shown in Fig.5. The technique for using the APSS is summarized by C. R. Fuller et al. The APSS has several point sensors and combined signals from the sensors. It can be used to estimate the modal amplitude of known system.

Fig.5: Configuration of array of point sensors system.

When the system is defined by a series of response characteristics such as mode shapes Ψ_{mn} . Then, the out-of-plane motion of the system is described by

$$w(x, y, t) = \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} A_{mn} \Psi_{mn}(x, y) e^{j\omega t} \quad (1)$$

where A_{mn} are modal amplitudes. The above relation can easily be written for other variables such as velocity, acceleration, strain etc. It is necessary to sample the structural response at J positions and represent its values as a vector w_s for measure or estimate a mode or state of the system. If the structural response is dominated by J modes and vector, then w_s is related to the system modal amplitudes and known mode shape functions as follows,

$$\begin{bmatrix} w_s^1 \\ \vdots \\ w_s^J \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \Psi_{11}^1 & & \Psi_{MN}^1 \\ & \ddots & \\ \Psi_{11}^J & & \Psi_{MN}^J \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} A_{11} \\ \vdots \\ A_{MN} \end{bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

where the elements of w_s comprise the measured complex displacements and $M+N=J$. The $e^{j\omega t}$ time factor has been omitted for convenience. By solving the above system of equations, we can obtain the modal amplitude as

$$\mathbf{a} = \Psi^{-1} \mathbf{w}_s \quad (3)$$

where $\mathbf{a}=[A_{11},A_{12},\dots,A_{12},\dots,A_{MN}]^T$, $\mathbf{w}_s=[w_s^1,w_s^2,\dots,w_s^J]^T$ and Ψ is a matrix of the modal contribution at the sample points. Thus if there is an array of J sensors on structure, the output of sensors can be processed by using Eqn 3 in order to obtain information related to individual modes.

SPECIMEN

The smart layer which has the PZT thin film sensors system is schematically shown in Fig.6. The specimen consists of a glass fiber reinforced plastic (GFRP) composite beam and the smart layer. The fiber orientation of the GFRP composite beam is $[+45^\circ_2/-45^\circ_2]_s$. The smart layer consists of four thin film PZT sensors and two flexible electric circuit sheets. The flexible electric circuit sheet is made of polyimide film and etched copper circuits. The thin film PZT sensors are sandwiched between the flexible electric circuit sheets. The thin film PZT sensors and the electric circuits are connected by a conductive adhesive and space between the electric circuits sheets is filled by an acrylate resin. The specimen is 190mm in length and 20mm in width. The thickness of the GFRP beam is 1.5mm and that of the smart layer is 0.25mm. The sensor numbers are defined as in Fig.6.

Fig. 6: Schematic view of smart layer.

EXPERIMENT

The experimental setup is shown in Fig.7. It consists of a signal generator, a vibrator, an A/D converter and a personal computer. The specimen is supported by clamped-clamped condition. The experiment is conducted by sinusoidal forced vibration tests. The signals from the sensors are sampled through the A/D converter. The signal processing and the modal estimation of the composite beam are carried out by a computer system. In case of the APSS, the sensor outputs are combined in the computer system for investigating its ability.

Fig.7: Experimental setup

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Characteristics of PZT Thin Film Sensor in Smart Layer

Fig.8 shows a comparison of the PZT thin film sensor output in the smart layer and the strain gage output. From this figure, it is found that the PZT thin film sensor has enough capability to detect vibration response of the GFRP composite beam. However, the PZT thin film sensor output is a little different from the strain gage output. This difference is caused by a hysteresis of the PZT thin film sensor.

Fig.8: A comparison of vibration response measured by PZT thin film sensor in smart layer and strain gage (1st mode, with Sensor 1).

Fig.9: Mode shape of deflection and strain on surface of composite beam.

The first three natural frequencies of the composite beam are obtained by the under clamped-clamped condition.

First Mode (185Hz)

The mode shape of deflection and the strain on the surface of the composite beam at the first mode are shown in Figs.9(a) and 9(b), respectively. The theoretical sensor outputs can be calculated by integrating of the strain on the surface of the composite beam along the gage length of the PZT thin film sensor. In case of the first mode, the ratio of each sensor output is 1:-0.72:-0.72:1 theoretically. The sensor outputs of the first mode are shown in Fig.10. Those figures show that all of sensors can detect the vibrations of each location. Moreover, the ratio of experimental sensor outputs has good agreement with the theoretical one.

Fig.10: PZT thin film sensor outputs (1st mode).

Second Mode (475Hz)

Figs.9(c) and 9(d) show the mode shape of deflection and the strain on the surface of the

composite beam at the second mode, respectively. In case of the second mode, the theoretical ratio of the sensor outputs is 1: -1.52:1.52:-1. The sensor outputs of the second mode is shown in Fig.11. The results can explain characteristics of the second mode. However, the ratio of the experimental sensor outputs is different from the theoretical ratio. This is due to the reason why as the natural frequency of experimental setup is close to the second mode of the composite beam, some noises are involved in the vibration response.

Fig.11: PZT thin film sensor outputs (2nd mode).

Third Mode (1500Hz)

The mode shape of deflection and the strain on the surface of the composite beam at the third mode are shown in Figs. 9(e) and 9(f), respectively. In case of the third mode, the theoretical ratio of the sensor outputs is 1:0.58:0.58:1. The sensor outputs of the third mode is shown in Fig.12. From those figures, it is found that the sensor outputs have distortions, however, the ratio of each sensor output agrees with the theoretical one. This result means that the PZT thin film sensor can detect high frequency vibration.

Fig.12: PZT thin film sensor outputs (3rd mode).

Array of Point Sensors System

The ratios of the sensor outputs and the combined sensor output are summarized Table 1. The gain ratio of the sensor outputs is 1:-0.5:1:0.5 for Sensor 1:Sensor 2:Sensor 3:Sensor 4. In case of a simple beam, mode shapes are not so complicated. Thus, the gains of sensor outputs can be chosen easily referring to Eqn 3. However, if the mode shape of structure is complicated, the gains of the sensor outputs have to be decided carefully. Fig.13 shows the combined sensor output of the first mode as well as the calculated sensor outputs of each sensor. From those figures, it is shown that the APSS can detect the vibrations of each sensor location. However, sensor outputs of the APSS are different from those of the DPSS. In the process of the APSS, all of the sensor outputs are summed, thus the calculated sensor outputs are smoothed.

Table 1: Ratio of sensor outputs and combined sensor output of array of point sensor.

	Sensor 1	Sensor 2	Sensor 3	Sensor 4	Combined sensor output
1st mode	1	-0.72	-0.72	1	2.36
2nd mode	1	-1.52	1.52	-1	2.78
3rd mode	1	0.58	0.58	1	1.21

Fig.13: Combined sensor output and calculated sensor output of each sensor.

CONCLUSIONS

In the present paper, the vibration modal estimation for the composite beam with the smart layer including PZT thin film sensors has been demonstrated. The results obtained here are summarized as follows;

- 1) The PZT thin film sensor has enough capability to detect vibration responses of the composite beam.
- 2) The PZT thin film sensor can detect high frequency vibration.
- 3) The distributed point sensors system can detect the absolute amplitudes and phases at all sensor points.
- 4) The array of point sensors system can estimate the amplitude, however the calculated signal outputs are averaged values.

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